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FORMATION OF REFLECTIVE COMPETENCIES IN FUTURE TEACHERS

Annotation: *During the long stretches of autonomy, the idea of making human resources that is in a profound way full-grown, genuinely impressive, intellectually progressed, ready to recognize changes and developments in the public arena without wasting any time was advanced. The educational calling is both a change and the board is One must be capable to deal with one's development. In this manner, the idea of youth ability mirrors his hypothetical and functional groundwork for the execution of educational exercises and a significant degree of expertise.*

Keywords: *instructor, reflection, capability, proficient ability, educational diagnostics, academic abilities.*

Arrangement of expert skill in preparing of future instructors on the planet, making of vital academic conditions for their expert and self-awareness in advanced education organizations, advancement of academic bases of development of expert capability of future educators, mental - There are issues, for example, the meaning of academic conditions and the validation of standards for deciding the degree of improvement of reflexive abilities focused on personal growth. Today, with regards to the financial improvement of society, the arrangement of reflexive abilities of instructors of instructive foundations is viewed as a significant measure for expanding the usefulness and proficiency of academic action.

Globally, the arrangement and improvement of the subject's reflexive experience, which incorporates data, instrumental, esteem persuasive and conduct parts, framed and created during the reflexive movement of the

subject, self-assurance, self-information, mindfulness self-assurance, self-plan and clear assignments for mindfulness, an arrangement of self-articulation abilities to tackle inward contentions in dangerous struggle circumstances, innovations for creating individual reflexive capability recognizable proof and application assume a significant part. This incredible feeling of obligation expects instructors to work on the different cycles of academic abilities at the degree of present-day necessities. Lately, instructors and clinicians have underscored the significance of fostering educators' reasoning and insightful abilities in their academic work. The premise of these abilities is the expert impression of educators.

Reflexing (lat. "Reflexus" - look back) - 1) Review, self-monitoring, self-awareness; Focus on the human inner world, spiritual quality and condition; tendency to self-analysis;

2) psychological-moving individuals, it is to understand how to be accepted by the partner of his dialogue. The idea of each other at the same time interacted. It has two sides: to assess each other and change some kind of property [1].

For the first time, the reflexing fall occurred in ancient Greek philosophy, and the process of conducting a person meant to attract the attention of his opinion to analyze the content of his thoughts (Descartes). Socrates, Plato, Locke and other Greek philosophers emphasize that reflection is aimed at acknowledging self-knowing, what is powerful. European philosophers such as Kant, Hegel, Fichte, Shelling, viewed the reflexes as the basis for the development of human knowledge. According to the concept of Leibniz, reflection is mentioned as a characteristic feature of human apperception (perception in human past and individual characteristics). In today's modern philosophy, reflexing differs from theoretical and practical anguish.

The first is the process of the development of concepts by man, as a method that gives the transition from one definition to another within the

uniform concept; the second is the process of interrogating an individual movement or opinion with a concept so that control over the incision measure provided.

The reflection which is being studied as a philosophical category is recognized and studied as an object of study in psychology, sociology, synergetics, logic, andrology, eukaryotes, cybernetics, and many other complex disciplines. We define the category of “reflection” from the point of view of pedagogy and psychology and discuss in detail the role of teachers in improving their pedagogical skills in the study of its essence.

In psychology, reflection interpreted as "knowing, controlling one's inner mental process and state."

In the pedagogical activity of the teacher and in the study of the importance of reflection on the individual, the perfection of the definition of the concept from the socio-psychological point of view emphasized. Reflection refers not only to the subject's self-knowledge or understanding, but also to how he or she is "reflected" by others and to his or her personal characteristics, emotional reactions, feelings, inner world, and cognitive imaginations.

By scientifically studying the possibilities of controlling the mental development of the individual, S.L. Rubinstein connects the existence of man and his relationship to social existence with reflection. "Reflection is a process that interrupts the continuous process of human life for a moment and takes a person beyond his imagination, in which case every action of a person acquires a certain character in his philosophical thoughts about life." he says. In this regard, it should be noted that reflection plays an important role in the professional activity of the student. According to B.Z.Vulfov, in the process of professional reflection, the student compares his / her abilities, existing ideas about him / her with the important aspects of his / her pedagogical experience to the extent required by the chosen pedagogical profession, and forms a “voluntary chain of personal

pedagogical skills” does. His opinion confirms L.S. Rubinstein's famous rule about the indirect action of external causes in pedagogical activity on the basis of internal conditions.

One of the main features of a teacher's pedagogical skills is the continuity of his development. This means that the reflexive process should not focus on the teacher's professional skills or professional qualities, but on encouraging their development, enrichment, and strengthening. The learning process should serve this purpose only when knowledge, skills, and competencies are consciously accepted with an internal urge for self-improvement. It is not always possible for a teacher to "perfect himself professionally in every way." Nevertheless, almost any thought about the teacher himself, almost every process of professional reflection, is important to make the professional activity interesting: hard work done with sincerity and kindness also facilitates professional activity; which is one of the foundations of the basic content and essence of reflection [3].

In the works of pedagogical scientists A. Golitsyn and G.P. Shedrovinsky, great attention is paid to reflection as a key factor and a natural mechanism for the development of the pedagogical activity. G.P. Schedrovitsky proposes to study reflection from the point of view of the "complex of positive activities" of man. He believes that if a pedagogical activity is not possible, the idea is to build a system of "reflexive exit" beyond this activity. In this case, a person moves from an unexplored activity to a new activity position and acquires the tools to "build meaning", from which he understands and describes the primary activity, using the second as an important "material" in the new activity.

Such conclusions of scientists are based on the fact that professional reflection is reflected in the enthusiasm of the teacher in self-development (which is determined by the fact that he can never be dissatisfied with the results of his creative work). So, reflection is also the basis for a teacher's self-improvement. In professional pedagogical activity, studying the

reflexive processes, it should be noted that reflection is not only an event related to the planning of pedagogical activity but also the essence of reflection is used to optimize professional activity. According to some scholars, reflection allows overcoming the old patterns and shortcomings accumulated in the experience of the teacher over the centuries, his behavior, communication culture, thinking (G. Pozhmelkina, Ye. Koloshina, Ye. Frolova). A teacher's professional reflection can be seen as a necessary part of pedagogical thinking. It helps the teacher to take an analytical approach to his / her professional activity, to determine his / her place in the pedagogical activity. It helps him to achieve positive results in his planned work, to find optimal ways to purposefully change his pedagogical activity and constructive means [4].

It allows the teacher to study the pedagogical activity, the theoretical conclusions made on the basis of many years of experience, the process of development of pedagogical skills on the basis of a five-element system.

Develop pedagogical skills based on the teacher's professional reflection

The process of self-knowledge takes place at the level of recording information within the framework of the teacher's pedagogical skills. In this case, the passive form of reflection prevails. The teacher simply records the reasons for the various difficulties and problems that arise in the pedagogical activity, the reasons for the achievements and problems, the achievements, and the results.

The process of self-awareness involves the teacher's ability to look at himself from the outside, to observe himself, in his own activity, and in a "meta-position" (uncertainty) towards himself. In this case, the phenomenon of internalization (the transition of external factors to internal factors) takes place, the causes of professional difficulties are formalized; the main goal of the activity is defined, reflexive - "I" is formed. It depends on the teacher's current level of development.

In the process of self-determination, the initial level is determined by the professional needs, and activities are planned based on rapid opportunities. Strategic, tactical, and operational tasks are formed. The real "I" and the ideal "I" are compared. It depends on the level of development of the teacher.

The process of self-development takes place during the teacher's professional career with the development of improved pedagogical skills, reflexive (methods that have been used before and have become increasingly optimal as a result of evaluating their effectiveness).

Self-monitoring implies the beginning of the second form of self-monitoring in the pedagogical activity of teachers based on theoretical and practical experience, professional self-monitoring, and further improvement of pedagogical skills.

It is accepted to look at diagnosis as a separate way of knowing (translated from Greek, it means diagnosis-recognition). Thus, there are aspects of its connection with pedagogical reflection. Pedagogical diagnostics performs many functions depending on the content and

essence. Its analytical task the diagnostic function is used to determine whether a student is educated, trained, and developed, but is also important in the study of a teacher's professional component level.

The task of evaluation of pedagogical diagnostics is carried out by the administration, which quantitatively evaluates the achievements and shortcomings of the individual teacher or individual student, as well as quality indicators. In this regard, we would like to emphasize that pedagogical diagnosis is effective when it has a predictive character of achievements in pedagogical activity. Experiments by scientists have shown that the defining (prognostic) nature of the study of pedagogical skills is based directly on the professional reflection of the teacher. This allows the teacher to determine exactly what the problem is in the educational process and what the cause is, and not to confuse cause and effect with the consequences of pedagogical difficulty. This is a specific indicator (calculation) function of pedagogical diagnoses, which allows you to quickly correct the professional activity of the teacher. Assessment of the teacher's potential should be taken into account in any case during the diagnosis, - says A.K.Markova, - it is necessary to trust him, to increase or decrease the value of his professional activity will improve the professional development of the student that can suspend. It is advisable to take into account the individual developmental logic of this teacher. A teacher's achievements should be compared not only with those of other teachers but also with their own.

The analysis of the scientific literature, as well as the use of diagnostic methods to improve the pedagogical skills of teachers in pedagogical activities and the analysis of the obtained results, allow to evaluate pedagogical diagnostics as one of the ways to ensure the development of teacher professional reflection. After all, in the study of best pedagogical practices, the teacher "plans the purpose and objectives of the study of experience, identifies relevant topics, studies the achievements of skilled

teachers in school practice, collects materials, analyzes, draws conclusions" use tools. We would also like to emphasize that pedagogical diagnosis is effective when it has a goal-setting (prognostic) character rather than a recording, which is based on the development of the teacher's professional reflection. At the same time, it is the goal-oriented diagnosis in the educational process that enables it to develop.

In short, the teacher's understanding of the results of his professional activity necessitates the search for and mastering of more advanced ways of carrying out his pedagogical activity. It is well known that mastering an activity leads to a change in the subject of activity. As a teacher's analytical (analytical) skills develop, so does his or her professional reflection, which in turn directs the teacher's self-development process in a certain direction and increases his or her personal creative activity.

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